

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

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GENERAL REMARKS

Reagents and solvents: All commercially available compounds were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Switzerland), Acros, Apollo Scientific, Alfa Aesar and Fluorochem (United Kingdom). Column chromatography was performed on silica gel P60 (40-63 μm) from SilicycleTM, the solvents were technical grade. TLC was performed with silica gel 60 F254 glass plates purchased from Merck.

Analyticals and instruments: NMR experiments were performed on Bruker Avance III NMR spectrometers operating at 250, 400, 500 or 600 (cryoprobe) MHz proton frequencies. The instruments were equipped with a direct-observe 5 mm BBFO smart probe (250, 400 MHz), or an indirect-detection 5 mm BBI probe (500 MHz), or a five-channel cryogenic 5 mm QCI probe (600 MHz). All probes were equipped with actively shielded z-gradients (10 A). The chemical shifts are reported in ppm relative to tetramethylsilane or referenced to residual solvent peak and the J values are given in Hz (± 0.1 Hz). Standard Bruker pulse sequences were used, and the data was processed on Topspin 3.2 (Bruker) using twofold zero-filling in the indirect dimension. High-resolution matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (HR- MALDI-ToF-MS) were performed on a solariX instrument from Bruker Daltonics. High-resolution electron spray ionization mass spectrometry (HR-ESI-MS) were performed on a maX-isTM4G instrument from Bruker. UV-vis absorption spectra were recorded at 20 °C on a Jasco V-770 Spectrophotometer. CD measurements were performed on a JASCO J-1500 CD Spectrophotometer. Automated recycling gel-permeation chromatography (GPC) was performed on a Shimadzu Prominence System equipped with SDV preparative columns from Polymer Standards Service (two Shodex columns in series, 20 x 600 mm each, exclusion limit: 30000 g/mol) with chloroform as solvent. High-pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC) was performed on a Shimadzu Prominence System. Single crystal X-ray diffraction data were collected at low temperature on a STOE STADIVARI or a Bruker Kappa Apex2 diffractometer with monochromated Ga $K\alpha$ or Cu $K\alpha$ radiation, respectively. Using Olex2, the structures were solved with the ShelXT structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the ShelXL refinement package using Least Squares minimization. Refinement was performed with anisotropic temperature factors for all non-hydrogen atoms (disordered atoms were refined isotropically); hydrogen atoms were calculated on idealized positions. Melting points were measured using a Stuart SMP3 melting point apparatus.

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION

(*S_p*)-**S1** representing *rac*-**S1**

rac-**S1** was synthesized according to literature,^[1] differing only in the use of racemic starting material. The product (*rac*-**S1**) was separated into its enantiomers (*R_p*)-**S1** and (*S_p*)-**S1** using chiral HPLC. The analytical data was recorded for the racemic mixture except of the CD, which was recorded after separation of the individual enantiomers.

TLC (SiO₂, cyclohexane/toluene/ethylacetate (15:2:1)): $R_f = 0.82$

¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K, δ /ppm): 7.00 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1H, H-7), 6.59 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H, H-4), 6.50 (dd, $J = 7.9, 2.0$ Hz, 1H, H-6), 3.54 – 3.44 (m, 1H, H_b-9), 3.28 (s, 1H, H-1), 3.13 – 3.04 (m, 2H, H_a-9 & H_b-10), 2.99 – 2.90 (m, 1H, H_a-10).

¹³C{¹H}-NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K, δ /ppm): 143.16 (C-8), 139.59 (C-5), 137.33 (C-4), 132.89 (C-6), 130.60 (C-7), 124.45 (C-3), 83.88 (C-2), 80.63 (C-1), 34.97 (C-10), 32.78 (C-9).

HRMS (ESI, +): m/z calcd. for C₁₆H₂₀Ag [M+Ag]⁺: 323.0297, found: 323.0298.

Figure S 1: ¹H-NMR spectrum of *rac*-S1 in CDCl₃.

Figure S 2: ¹³C{¹H}-NMR spectrum of *rac*-S1 in CDCl₃.

Figure S 3: **COSY** spectrum of *rac-S1* in CDCl₃.

Figure S 4: **NOESY** spectrum of *rac-S1* in CDCl₃.

Figure S 5: HMQC spectrum of *rac*-S1 in CDCl₃.

Figure S 6: HMBC spectrum of *rac*-S1 in CDCl₃.

High Resolution Mass Spectrometry Report

Sample Name **zwp-962**
Comment

Instrument **maXis 4G**
Method **ms_nocolumn_mid_pos.m**

Figure S 7: HRMS (ESI, +) spectrum of *rac*-S1.

Figure S 8: Preparative HPLC chromatogram of the chiral resolution of *rac*-S1. Separation was performed using a CHIRALPAK IBN-5 column (30 x 250 mm, *n*-heptane/EtOH 98:2, flowrate = 42 mL/min). Assignment of the absolute configuration was done by analytical enantiomeric separation of (*rac*)-4,15-diformyl[2.2]paracyclophane according to literature,^[1] followed by a Ohira-Bestmann modification of the Seyferth-Gilbert homologation and comparison of the circular dichroism spectra.

Synthesis of $(S_p)_3-1_3$, $(S_p)_4-1_4$, $(S_p)_5-1_5$, and $(S_p)_6-1_6$: *Preparation of reagents:* CuCl (15 g) was purified by washing it with aqueous HCl (1 M) and drying it under vacuum. Cu(OAc)₂ (10 g) was purified by refluxing in Ac₂O (50 mL) overnight, filtering it under N₂, washing with THF and drying under vacuum.

Synthetic Procedure: A dry two-neck round-bottom flask was charged with dry pyridine (165 mL), copper (I) chloride (583 mg, 5.89 mmol, 18 eq.) and copper (II) acetate (1.663 g, 9.16 mmol, 28 eq.). The solution was degassed by purging with argon for 1 hour and heated to 80 °C. (S_p) -**S1** (84 mg, 327 μmol, 1.0 eq.) was dissolved in pyridine (55 mL), degassed by purging with argon for 1 hour and added dropwise with a dropping funnel to the pyridine copper solution. After 18 h the reaction mixture was allowed to cool down to room temperature and the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The residue was suspended in CH₂Cl₂, washed with HCl (1 M, 2x), brine and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solid residue was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO₂, cyclohexane/toluene/ethylacetate, 15:2:1) and the combined fractions comprising the macrocyclic products were concentrated and subjected to automated recycling gel-permeation chromatography (GPC), where analytically pure $(S_p)_3-1_3$ (24 mg, 108 μmol, 29%) and $(S_p)_4-1_4$ (17 mg, 81.8 μmol, 20%) were isolated as the slowest and second slowest eluting band, respectively. The third and fourth eluting band were each concentrated and subjected to normal-phase HPLC to give $(S_p)_5-1_5$ (6 mg,

65.4 μmol , 7%) and (S_p)₆-**16** (1 mg, 0.65 μmol , 1.2%), respectively. All macrocycles were isolated as white solids.

The synthesis of the (R_p)-enantiomers was performed identically and the analytical data matched the data of the (S_p)-enantiomers.

Analytical data of (S_p)₃-**13**:

M.p.: > 350°C

TLC (SiO₂, cyclohexane/toluene/ethylacetate (15:2:1)): R_f = 0.71

¹H-NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K, δ /ppm): 7.09 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 1H, H-7), 6.65 – 6.54 (m, 2H, H-4 & H-6), 3.83 – 3.75 (m, 1H, H_a-9), 3.47 – 3.39 (m, 1H, H_b-9), 3.30 – 3.25 (m, 1H, H_b-10), 2.86 – 2.78 (m, 1H, H_a-10).

¹³C{¹H}-NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K, δ /ppm): 146.52 (C8), 139.98 (C5), 133.87 (C4), 133.00 (C6), 131.79 (C7), 123.74 (C3), 88.19 (C2), 80.69 (C1), 35.31 (C10), 34.35 (C9).

HR-MS (MALDI-ToF, +): m/z calcd. for C₆₀H₄₂Ag [M+Ag]⁺: 869.2332, found: 869.2342.

Analytical data of (S_p)₄-**14**:

M.p.: > 350°C

TLC (SiO₂, cyclohexane/toluene/ethylacetate (15:2:1)): R_f = 0.60

¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K, δ /ppm): 7.10 (d, J = 7.8 Hz, 1H, H-7), 6.62 (d, J = 1.9 Hz, 1H, H-4), 6.58 (dd, J = 7.9, 1.9 Hz, 1H, H-6), 3.84 – 3.74 (m, 1H, H_a-9), 3.38 – 3.28 (m, 1H, H_b-9), 3.26 – 3.16 (m, 1H, H_b-10), 2.96 – 2.85 (m, 1H, H_a-10).

¹³C{¹H}-NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K, δ /ppm): 145.46 (C8), 139.90 (C5), 135.74 (C4), 133.03 (C6), 131.46 (C7), 124.02 (C3), 84.15 (C2), 78.83 (C1), 35.13 (C10), 33.82 (C9).

HR-MS (MALDI-ToF, +): m/z calcd. for C₈₀H₅₆Ag [M+Ag]⁺: 1123.3427, found: 1123.3447.

Analytical data of (S_p)₅-**15**:

M.p.: > 350°C

TLC (SiO₂, cyclohexane/toluene/ethylacetate (15:2:1)): R_f = 0.45

¹H-NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K, δ /ppm): 7.10 (d, J = 7.8 Hz, 1H, H-7), 6.66 (d, J = 1.9 Hz, 1H, H-4), 6.57 (dd, J = 7.9, 1.9 Hz, 1H, H-6), 3.76 – 3.68 (m, 1H, H_a-9), 3.33 – 3.24 (m, 1H, H_b-9), 3.22 – 3.12 (m, 1H, H_b-10), 2.99 – 2.91 (m, 1H, H_a-10).

¹³C{¹H}-NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K, δ/ppm): 144.66 (C8), 139.90 (C5), 136.80 (C4), 133.15 (C6), 131.37 (C7), 124.09 (C3), 82.88 (C2), 78.10 (C1), 35.06 (C10), 33.49 (C9).

HR-MS (MALDI-ToF, +): *m/z* calcd. for C₁₀₀H₇₀Ag [M+Ag]⁺: 1377.4523, found: 1377.4546.

Analytical data of (S_p)₆-1₆:

M.p.: > 350°C

TLC (SiO₂, cyclohexane/toluene/ethylacetate (15:2:1)): R_f = 0.33

¹H-NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K, δ/ppm): 7.08 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H, H-7), 6.69 (d, *J* = 1.9 Hz, 1H, H-4), 6.57 (dd, *J* = 7.9, 1.9 Hz, 1H, H-6), 3.74 – 3.65 (m, 1H, H_a-9), 3.30 – 3.23 (m, 1H, H_b-9), 3.20 – 3.12 (m, 1H, H_b-10), 3.02 – 2.93 (m, 1H, H_a-10).

¹³C{¹H}-NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K, δ/ppm): 144.25 (C8), 139.91 (C5), 137.37 (C4), 133.27 (C6), 131.37 (C7), 124.17 (C3), 82.64 (C2), 77.83 (C1), 35.06 (C10), 33.45 (C9).

HR-MS (MALDI-ToF, +): *m/z* calcd. for C₁₂₀H₈₄ [M]⁺: 1524.6568, found: 1524.6567.

Figure S 9: ^1H -NMR spectrum of $(S_p)_3\text{-13}$ in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 10: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR spectrum of $(S_p)_3\text{-13}$ in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 11: COSY spectrum of $(S_p)_3-13$ in $CDCl_3$.

Figure S 12: NOESY spectrum of $(S_p)_3-13$ in $CDCl_3$.

Figure S 13: HSQC spectrum of $(S_p)_3-13$ in $CDCl_3$.

Figure S 14: HMBC spectrum of $(S_p)_3-13$ in $CDCl_3$.

Acquisition Parameter

Method:	MALDI_MS_POS_300-2600_2M_16AvScans	Acquisition Date:	11.10.2021 12:00:52		
File Name:	D:\Data\ETH Data\BSOL0015xx\BSOL001571_0_D18_000001.d	Operator:	Michael Meier		
Source	Dual (MALDI/ESI)	Polarity	Positive	Nebulizer Gas	1.3 bar
Broadband Low Mass	303.1 m/z	Laser Power	35.0 lp	Drying Gas Flow Rate	3.7 L/min
Broadband High Mass	2600.0 m/z			Capillary	2800.0 V
No. of Cell Fills	1	Time of Flight to Detector	0.001 sec	Drying Gas	200.0 °C
Apodization	Full-Sine			Temperature	

Figure S 15: HRMS (MALDI-ToF, +) spectrum of $(S_p)_3-1_3$.

Figure S 16: ^1H -NMR spectrum of $(S_p)_4\text{-14}$ in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 17: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR spectrum of $(S_p)_4\text{-14}$ in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 18: COSY spectrum of $(S_p)_4$ -14 in $CDCl_3$.

Figure S 19: NOESY spectrum of $(S_p)_4$ -14 in $CDCl_3$.

Figure S 20: **HMQC** spectrum of $(S_p)_4\text{-14}$ in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 21: **HMBC** spectrum of $(S_p)_4\text{-14}$ in CDCl_3 .

Acquisition Parameter

Method:	MALDI_MS_POS_300-2600_2M_16AvScans			Acquisition Date:	11.10.2021 11:48:49
File Name:	D:\Data\ETH Data\BSOL0015xx\BSOL001572_0_D20_000001.d			Operator:	Michael Meier
Source	Dual (MALDI/ESI)	Polarity	Positive	Nebulizer Gas	1.3 bar
Broadband Low Mass	303.1 m/z	Laser Power	35.0 lp	Drying Gas Flow Rate	3.7 L/min
Broadband High Mass	2600.0 m/z	Time of Flight to Detector	0.001 sec	Capillary	2800.0 V
No. of Cell Fills	1			Drying Gas	200.0 °C
Apodization	Full-Sine			Temperature	

Figure S 22: HRMS (MALDI-ToF, +) spectrum of $(S_p)_4-14$.

Figure S 23: ¹H-NMR spectrum of $(S_p)_5-15$ in CDCl₃.

Figure S 24: ¹³C(¹H)-NMR spectrum of $(S_p)_5-15$ in CDCl₃.

Figure S 25: **COSY** spectrum of $(S_p)_5-15$ in $CDCl_3$.

Figure S 26: **NOESY** spectrum of $(S_p)_5-15$ in $CDCl_3$.

Figure S 27: HSQC spectrum of $(S_p)_5\text{-15}$ in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 28: HMBC spectrum of $(S_p)_5\text{-15}$ in CDCl_3 .

Acquisition Parameter

Method:	MALDI_MS_POS_300-2600_2M_16AvScans	Acquisition Date:	11.10.2021 11:54:33
File Name:	D:\Data\ETH Data\BSOL0015xx\BSOL001573_0_D22_000001.d	Operator:	Michael Meier
Source	Dual (MALDI/ESI)	Polarity	Positive
Broadband Low Mass	303.1 m/z	Nebulizer Gas	1.3 bar
Broadband High Mass	2600.0 m/z	Drying Gas Flow Rate	3.7 L/min
No. of Cell Fills	1	Laser Power	35.0 lp
Apodization	Full-Sine	Time of Flight to Detector	0.001 sec
		Drying Gas Temperature	2800.0 V
			200.0 °C

Figure S 29: HRMS (MALDI-ToF, +) spectrum of (S_p)₅-1₅.

*Figure S 30: Preparative HPLC chromatogram of $(S_p)_5-15$ isolated from the GPC. Separation was performed using a Reprosil Si column (30 x 250 mm, *n*-heptane/ CH_2Cl_2 75:25, flowrate = 42 mL/min).*

Figure S 31: ^1H -NMR spectrum of $(\text{S}_p)_6\text{-16}$ in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 32: $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR spectrum of $(\text{S}_p)_6\text{-16}$ in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 33: **COSY** spectrum of $(S_p)_6\text{-16}$ in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 34: **NOESY** spectrum of $(S_p)_6\text{-16}$ in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 35: HSQC spectrum of $(S_p)_6-16$ in $CDCl_3$.

Figure S 36: HMBC spectrum of $(S_p)_6-16$ in $CDCl_3$.

Acquisition Parameter

Method:	MALDI_MS_POS_300-2600_2M_16AvScans	Acquisition Date:	06.04.2022 08:37:32
File Name:	D:\Data\ETH Data\BSOL0017xx\BSOL001707_0_F24_000001.d	Operator:	Michael Meier
Source:	Dual (MALDI/ESI)	Polarity:	Positive
Broadband Low Mass:	303.1 m/z	Nebulizer Gas:	1.3 bar
Broadband High Mass:	2600.0 m/z	Drying Gas Flow Rate:	3.7 L/min
No. of Cell Fills:	1	Capillary:	3000.0 V
Apodization:	Full-Sine	Drying Gas Temperature:	200.0 °C
		Time of Flight to Detector:	0.001 sec

Figure S 37: HRMS (MALDI-ToF, +) spectrum of $(S_p)_6-16$.

*Figure S 38: Analytical HPLC chromatogram of (S_p)₆-1₆ isolated from the GPC. Separation was performed using a Reprosil Si column (30 x 250 mm, *n*-heptane/CH₂Cl₂/THF 90:4:6, flowrate = 42 mL/min).*

GPC DATA

Figure S 39: **GPC chromatogram** of the reaction mixture with the improved conditions. The peaks corresponding to $(S_p)_3-1_3$ (orange), $(S_p)_4-1_4$ (blue), $(S_p)_5-1_5$ (red), and $(S_p)_6-1_6$ (green) are displayed.

Figure S 40: GPC chromatogram of the reaction mixture using the initial conditions. The peaks corresponding to $(S_p)_3-1_3$ (orange), $(S_p)_4-1_4$ (blue), and $(S_p)_5-1_5$ (red) are displayed. Timestamps of which a UV spectrum is shown in the respective Figure S41-S43 are displayed by purple dashed lines.

==== Shimadzu LabSolutions UV Spectrum ====

UV Spectrum

: 1
Retention Time : 163.208 min
Compound Name :
Spectrum Operation : None

Figure S 41: UV-spectrum of the GPC peak at 163 minutes.

==== Shimadzu LabSolutions UV Spectrum ====

UV Spectrum

: 1
Retention Time : 158.414 min
Compound Name :
Spectrum Operation : None

Figure S 42: UV-spectrum of the GPC peak at 158 minutes.

==== Shimadzu LabSolutions UV Spectrum ====

UV Spectrum
: 1
Retention Time : 151.322 min
Compound Name :
Spectrum Operation : None

Figure S 43: **UV-spectrum** of the GPC peak at 151 minutes.

UV-VIS DILUTION SERIES

Figure S 44: Dilution series of the absorption of $(R_p)_3-1_3$ in CH_2Cl_2 .

Figure S 45: Linear regression of the absorption at 332 nm of $(R_p)_3-1_3$ in CH_2Cl_2 versus concentration.

Figure S 46: **Dilution series** of the absorption of $(R_p)_4\text{-14}$ in CH_2Cl_2 .

Figure S 47: **Linear regression** of the absorption at 340 nm of $(R_p)_4\text{-14}$ in CH_2Cl_2 versus concentration.

Figure S 48: Dilution series of the absorption of $(R_p)_5-1s$ in CH_2Cl_2 .

Figure S 49: Linear regression of the absorption at 340 nm of $(R_p)_5-1s$ in CH_2Cl_2 versus concentration.

Figure S 50: Dilution series of the absorption of $(R_p)_6-16$ in CH_2Cl_2 .

Figure S 51: Linear regression of the absorption at 340 nm of $(R_p)_6-16$ in CH_2Cl_2 versus concentration.

g-FACTOR PLOT

Figure S 52: **g-Factor** plot of $(S_p)_3-1_3$, $(S_p)_4-1_4$, $(S_p)_5-1_5$, and $(S_p)_6-1_6$.

CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC DATA (CCDC 2172361)

Table S1. Crystal data and structure refinement for (*R_p*)**4-14**.

Identification code	(<i>R_p</i>) 4-14
Empirical formula	C ₈₂ H ₅₉ N
Formula weight	1058.30
Temperature/K	150
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁
a/Å	16.6923(5)
b/Å	7.4232(2)
c/Å	26.6152(8)
α/°	90
β/°	92.294(3)
γ/°	90
Volume/Å ³	3295.25(17)
Z	2
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.067
μ/mm ⁻¹	0.296
F(000)	1116.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.14 × 0.03 × 0.02
Radiation	GaKα (λ = 1.34143)
2θ range for data collection/°	7.252 to 117.948
Index ranges	-20 ≤ h ≤ 21, -9 ≤ k ≤ 4, -33 ≤ l ≤ 23
Reflections collected	23021
Independent reflections	10064 [R _{int} = 0.0323, R _{sigma} = 0.0418]
Data/restraints/parameters	10064/1/749
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.018
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0629, wR ₂ = 0.1786
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.1057, wR ₂ = 0.2003
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.18/-0.20
Flack parameter	9.2(8)

Figure S 53: ORTEP-representation of the unit cell of (R_p) -4-14. Hydrogens and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity. Ellipsoids are plotted on a 50% probability level.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Meyer-Eppler, R. Sure, A. Schneider, G. Schnakenburg, S. Grimme, A. Lützen, *J. Org. Chem.* **2014**, 79, 6679–6687.